

Heterocyclic Compounds. Part XXXVII. Synthesis of Scopoletin

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Scopoletin or 7-hydroxy-6-methoxycoumarin has been synthesised by three different routes: (a) By oxidising 7-mesyloxy- or 7-tosyloxy-coumarin with alkaline potassium persulphate to 7-mesyloxy- or 7-tosyloxy-6-hydroxycoumarin, which on methylation and subsequent removal of the mesyl or tosyl group provides scopoletin. (b) Preferential tosylation of 6,7-dihydroxycoumarin to 7-tosyloxy-6-hydroxycoumarin, methylation of the latter, and subsequent removal of the tosyl group also provide scopoletin. (c) Oxidation of the 6,7-dimethoxycoumarin by alkaline potassium persulphate takes an abnormal course, resulting in the formation of scopoletin.

Synthesis of 7-hydroxy-6-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin or 4-methylscopoletin by three different methods was effected by Desai and co-workers¹⁻³. The present communication describes the various methods of synthesis of scopoletin or 7-hydroxy-6-methoxycoumarin, a preliminary note⁴ on which was published sometime previously.

7-Hydroxycoumarin (I: R=H) was mesylated to 7-mesyloxy~~coumarin~~ (I: R=mesyl) which on oxidation by alkaline potassium persulphate furnished 7-mesyloxy-6-hydroxycoumarin (II: R=mesyl; R₁=H). This was methylated to 7-mesyloxy-6-methoxycoumarin (II: R=mesyl; R₁=Me) which on elimination of the mesyl group with H₂SO₄ (conc.) yielded 7-hydroxy-6-methoxycoumarin or scopoletin (II: R=H; R₁=Me).

The second synthesis involved protection of the hydroxyl group of 7-hydroxycoumarin by tosylation before oxidising it with alkaline persulphate, methylation of the hydroxyl group, and removal of the tosyl group with the formation of scopoletin. In view of the recent publication by Patel and Sethna⁵ on the same subject, experimental details have been curtailed.

The third method deals with the preferential monotosylation of ~~6,7-dihydroxy~~ hydroxycoumarin, resulting in 7-tosyloxy-6-hydroxycoumarin which on methylation and subsequent removal of the tosyl group provides scopoletin. This is considered to be the most efficient method of synthesising scopoletin.

The fourth method is the abnormal oxidation of 6,7-dimethoxycoumarin by alkaline potassium persulphate, resulting in the formation of scopoletin. The experimental details of this oxidation are precisely similar to those of the oxidation of 6,7-dimethoxy-4-methyl-

1. Bhavsar and Desai, *Ind. J. Phar.*, 1951, 13, 200.
2. *Idem*, this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 141.
3. Desai and Parghi, *ibid.*, 1956, 33, 483.
4. Bhavsar and Desai, *Curr. Sci.*, 1951, 20, 325.
5. This *Journal*, 1962, 39, 511.

coumarin which gives rise to 4-methylscopoletin. Experimental details, having been published previously³, have been omitted.

EXPERIMENTAL

7-Mesyloxy-7-mesyloxy coumarin.—To a mechanically stirred solution of 7-hydroxycoumarin (8.0 g.) and methanesulphonyl chloride (6.0 g.) in acetone (100 ml) a solution of sodium bicarbonate (9.0 g.) in water (50 ml) was added in four or five lots. After continued stirring for 4 hours, the mixture was poured in water when the mesyloxy derivative separated as a solid. It was washed with 1% NaOH solution to remove the unchanged coumarin and crystallised from ethanol in white needles, m. p. 148°. (Found: S, 13.0. $C_{10}H_8O_6S$ requires S, 13.3%.)

6-Hydroxy-7-mesyloxy coumarin.—To the cooled and mechanically stirred solution of the above mesyloxy coumarin (3.0 g.) in pyridine (75 ml) solutions of KOH (6.0 g.) in water (60 ml) and potassium persulphate (6.0 g.) in water (50 ml) were gradually added alternately during 3 hours. The red solution with blue fluorescence was stirred for 6 hours and set aside for 24 hours. On acidifying the solution to Congo red with HCl (conc.), the unchanged material separating was collected; the solution was extracted with ether which provided some more material (0.8 g.). The solution was then treated with sodium sulphite (6.0 g.) and HCl (conc., 80 ml), warmed on a water bath for 1 hour, and cooled. The solid separating was removed and other extraction of the solution provided another lot. The solid was treated with 2% sodium bicarbonate solution and the residue (0.75 g.) crystallised from rectified spirit in white plates, m. p. 220°. It dissolved in alkali with a deep yellow colour without any fluorescence; its ethanolic solution showed blue fluorescence. (Found: S, 12.8. $C_{10}H_8O_6S$ requires S, 12.5%.)

8-Methoxy-7-mesyloxy coumarin was prepared by refluxing the mixture of the above coumarin (0.5 g.), anhydrous potassium carbonate (3.0 g.), dimethyl sulphate (1.0 ml), and anhydrous acetone (50 ml) for 24 hours. The residue left after removal of acetone was treated with water. The insoluble product was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m. p. 153°. (Found: S, 11.70. $C_{11}H_{10}O_6S$ requires S, 11.85%.)

6-Methoxy-7-hydroxycoumarin (scopoletin) was obtained by keeping the solution of the preceding compound (0.5 g.) in H_2SO_4 (conc., 15 ml) for 24 hours and pouring it over ice. The solid, purified, through a dilute solution of NaOH, was crystallised from dilute ethanol in needles, m. p. 202–203°. Head and Robertson⁶ and Seka and Kallir⁷, who previously

6. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1241.

7. *Ber.*, 1931, 64B, 909.

synthesised this compound by different methods, recorded m.p. 204° and 202° respectively. (Found: C, 62.4; H, 4.20. Calc. for $C_{16}H_8O_4$: C, 62.50; H, 4.25%).

6-Hydroxy-7-tosyloxycoumarin.—A mixture of 6,7-dihydroxycoumarin (2.0 g.), *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (2.0 g.), anhydrous potassium carbonate (8.0 g.), and anhydrous acetone (75ml) was refluxed on a water bath for 7 hours. After removal of acetone, the solid was treated with a dilute NaOH solution, when the di-tosyl derivative (0.8 g.) remained insoluble. The non-fluorescent alkali solution on acidification with HCl furnished a solid (1.2 g.) which crystallised from ethanol in plates, m. p. 203°. (Found: S, 9.50. $C_{16}H_{14}O_6S$ requires S, 9.64%).

6-Methoxy-7-tosyloxycoumarin was prepared by refluxing a mixture of the above coumarin (0.5 g.), anhydrous potassium carbonate (3.0 g.), dimethyl sulphate (1.0 ml), and anhydrous acetone (50 ml) for 24 hours. The residue left after removal of acetone crystallised from dilute ethanol in thin white needles, m.p. 194-95°. (Found: S, 9.10. $C_{17}H_{14}O_6S$ requires S, 9.25%).

Scopletin was obtained by pouring the solution of the above coumarin in H_2SO_4 (conc., 0.3g. in 10 ml of the acid) after 24 hours over ice. It was identified by its m.p. and mixed m. p. with a specimen prepared by other methods.

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